

Derivation and compounding in english: A theoretical, structural, and semantic analysis

Usmonaliyeva Mohizarbonu Shavkatjon qizi

Fergana state university

Faculty of foreign languages 4th year student

ismoilovamohizar2005@gmail.com +998904076097

Karimjonova Shakhlo Ravshanjonovna

Supervisor: Doctor of Sciences, senior lecturer

Annotatsiya. *Ingliz tili doimo o'zgarib boradi va texnologiya, fan hamda kundalik hayotdagi yangiliklar tufayli yangi so'zlar paydo bo'ladi. Ushbu tadqiqot so'z yasashining ikki asosiy usuli, ya'ni derivatsiya va kompozitsiyani turli jihatdan o'rganadi. Konstruktiv Morfologiya eng foydali nazariya sifatida aniqlandi, chunki u ham keng tarqalgan modellarni, hamda o'zgarish shakllarni tushuntiradi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, prefikslar so'z turkumini odatda o'zgartirmaydi, suffikslar esa ko'pincha o'zgartiradi. Ko'plab yasama so'zlar vaqt o'tishi bilan yangi ma'no kasb etadi. Konversiya va orqaga yasash ham ko'rib chiqilgan. Bu natijalar O'zbekistonda ingliz tilini o'qitish va tarjima sohasida foydali bo'lishi mumkin.*

Kalit so'zlar. *So'z yasashi, derivatsiya, kompozitsiya, morfologiya, unumdorlik, leksikalizatsiya, Konstruktiv Morfologiya, orqaga yasash.*

Abstract. *The English language is always changing and new words are regularly created to keep up with progress in technology, science, and everyday life. This study looks at two main ways of forming new words, derivation and compounding, and examines them from different angles. Construction Morphology was found to be the most useful theory because it explains both common word patterns and fixed expressions. The results show that prefixes usually keep the same word class while suffixes often change it. Many derived words also gain new meanings over time. Conversion and back-formation are discussed as well. These findings can be helpful for teaching English and for translation work in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords. *Word formation, derivation, compounding, morphology, productivity, lexicalization, Construction Morphology, back-formation.*

The vocabulary of any living language grows constantly, and English is no exception. New words are needed every year to name new technologies, social changes, and scientific discoveries. English meets this need mainly through two internal processes: derivation, which involves building new words by adding prefixes or suffixes to existing bases, and compounding, which refers to joining two independent words into a single new unit. The present research examines both processes from theoretical, structural, and semantic perspectives (Plag I., 2003, -P. 1-5).

Word formation is defined as the creation of new lexemes, that is, independent vocabulary items with their own meanings, from the language's own resources (Matthews PH., 1991, -P. 65). It differs

from inflection, which only produces grammatical variants of an existing word, like *cat* and *cats*, because it produces genuinely new words, *teach* and *teacher*. The analysis is organized around two key concepts. Productivity measures how freely a rule generates new forms (Bauer L., 2001, -P. 12). For instance, the suffix *-ness* can be added to virtually any adjective, such as *boldness*, *mindfulness* and *wokeness*, and it is therefore fully productive, whereas the old suffix *-th*, as in *warmth* and *depth*, is no longer used to coin new words. Motivation describes how transparent a word's meaning is (Plag I., 2003, -P. 44). Fully motivated words like *unkind* mean exactly what their parts suggest; partially motivated ones like *blackboard* have a conventionalized meaning that goes beyond simple composition; and fully lexicalized words like *understand* have meanings entirely disconnected from their morphological parts.

Three theoretical models inform the research. The generative approach treats word formation as formal rules that specify which affixes combine with which bases (Marchand H., 1969, -P. 11). The lexicalist approach locates this process in the lexicon, keeping it separate from syntax (Booij G., 2010, -P. 3). Construction Morphology treats word-formation patterns as form-meaning schemas stored in the mental grammar, an approach that best accounts for both productive and lexicalized forms within a single framework. The research also highlights the two historical layers of English morphology: the native Germanic stratum, *un-*, *-ness*, *-ful*, *-less*, and the Latinate stratum, *re-*, *dis-*, *-tion*, *-ize*, *-able*, each with its own distributional patterns (Crystal D., 2003, -P. 128).

The analysis of derivation shows that prefixes are mainly class-maintaining, meaning they modify meaning without changing the grammatical category of the base, like in *un-* + *happy* = *unhappy*, while suffixes are mainly class-changing, *teach* + *-er* = *teacher* (Quirk R., 1985, -P. 1569). The most productive suffixes in contemporary English include *-ness*, *-er*, *-tion*, *-ize*, and *-able*; the most productive prefixes include *un-*, *re-*, *non-*, and *over-*. Most affixes are polysemous, as the suffix *-er*, for example, forms both agent nouns, such as *writer* and instrument nouns like *blender* (Plag I., 2003, -P. 132). Many derived words also undergo lexicalization over time: the computing sense of *driver* has diverged completely from the morphological meaning “one who drives” (Bauer L., 2001, -P. 67).

Beyond affixation, conversion that is using a word in a new grammatical category without any formal change: *to text*, *to google*, and back-formation, removing an apparent suffix: *editor* and *to edit*, further extend the derivational system, both driven by morphological analogy (Bauer L., 1983, -P. 200).

In conclusion, the research demonstrates that derivation is a systematic yet flexible process at the heart of English vocabulary development. Productivity, motivation, and lexicalization together explain how the derived vocabulary grows, stabilizes, and diversifies. Construction Morphology provides the most unified theoretical framework for this analysis, and the historical layering of English morphology underlies the distributional patterns observed in contemporary affixation. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of English morphology and offer practical insights for language teaching and translation in the Uzbek educational context (Bauer L., 1983, -P. 20).

References

1. Aronoff M. (1976). *Word Formation in Generative Grammar*. (-P. 134). Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
2. Bauer L. (1983). *English Word-Formation*. (-P. 20-200). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

3. Akbaraliyevich, L. A. (2025). THE INFLUENCE OF ENGLISH LOANWORDS ON THE MODERN UZBEK LANGUAGE. *SHOKH LIBRARY*, 1(12).
4. Latipov, A. (2020). THE FRAMEWORK OF THE THEORY OF “DEVELOPMENT OF THE SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION”. *Интернаука*, (19-4), 21-23.
5. Sevinchbonu, M., Parvina, A., & Akbaraliyevich, L. A. (2026). COLOR TERMS IN ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGY AND PAREMIOLOGY. *Advances in Science and Humanities*, 2(07), 6-10.
6. Akbaraliyevich, L. A. (2023). CONTEXTUAL MEANS OF EXPRESSING PHASE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT*, 2(4).
7. Хайруллаев, Х. З. (2012). Об иерархических отношениях между языковыми единицами. *Вестник Челябинского государственного университета*, (6 (260)), 134-137.
8. Турниёзов, Н., Турниёзова, К., & Хайруллаев, Х. (2009). Структур синтаксис асослари.
9. Хайруллаев, Х. (2008). Нутқ бирликларининг поғонали муносабати.
10. Yuldashevna, R. D. (2026). MASHG ‘ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA PEDAGOGIK DASTURIY VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING SAMARADORLIGI. *OLIY TA’LIM TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: DOLZARB TENDENSIYALAR VA STRATEGIYALAR*, 1(1), 1070-1075.
11. Urazaliyeva, I. R., Ramanova, D. Y., & Jo’raboyeva, D. N. (2026). EVALUATION OF THE COMBINED PREVENTIVE EFFICACY OF HORMONAL THERAPY AND LIFESTYLE INTERVENTIONS IN WOMEN WITH POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME. *Eureka Journal of Health Sciences & Medical Innovation*, 2(1), 672-682.
12. Khaydarov, N., & Ramanova, D. (2024). COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF BURNOUT SYNDROME IN NURSES. *Collection of scientific papers «SCIENTIA»*, (February 23 2024; Amsterdam, Netherlands), 284-286.
13. Khaydarov, N. K., Ramanova, D. Y., & Usmanbekova, G. K. (2021). MANIFESTATIONS OF BURNOUT SYNDROME IN LISTENERS OF NURSING ADVANCED TRAINING COURSES. *Журнал " Медицина и инновации "*, (4), 86-90.
14. Mamirova, D. (2026). SOCIOLINGUISTIC RESEARCH OF ADVERTISING TEXTS. *Asian journal of scientific research and innovations*, 1(1), 155-157.
15. Обруева, Г. Х. (2005). К ВОПРОСУ ОБ ИЗУЧЕНИИ ВО ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦАХ ОНО-МАСТИЧЕСКИХ КОМПОНЕНТОВ (на материале современного английского языка). *MATN LINGVISTIKASI (ilmiy to ‘plam)*.
16. Обруева, Г. О НЕКОТОРЫХ ОСОБЕННОСТЯХ УПОТРЕБЛЕНИЯ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ С ИМЕНАМИ СОБСТВЕННЫМИ. *ГОЛОВНИЙ РЕДАКТОР*, 327.
17. Mamirova, D. (2024). REKLAMA MATNLARIDA XRONOTOPNING LINGVISTIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Innovation: The journal of Social Sciences and Researches*, 2(1), 45-47.
18. GX, O. (2023). Frazeologiyaning dolzarb masalalari. *Samarqand: SamDCHTI*.

-
19. Abduraximova, F. K. (2022). Modern approaches and methods in teaching English language. *Экономика и социум*, (1-1 (92)), 10-13.
 20. Abduraximova, F., & Arikan, A. (2026). THE IMPORTANCE OF VOCABULARY ACQUISITION IN EFL LEARNING. *EDUCATION AND RESEARCH IN THE ERA OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION*, 522-526.
 21. Yule G. (2020). *The Study of Language*. 7th ed. (-P. 294). Cambridge: CUP.